

Managing Students' Unrest In Universities: Unmasking The Threat And Success Implication Through Ubuntu

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Article Info

Article History

Received:
July 07, 2020

Accepted:
September 01, 2020

Keywords

Students' unrest
University authorities
Ubuntu
Management
University productivity
Student performance.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.4010838

Abstract

Observations, practical experiences and literature confirmed that students' oriented crisis, unrest and protest continue unabated in the university system. Despite so much concerted efforts by the universities, scholars and government to ameliorate this, it seems the university authorities are not cognisance of some threatening social and human factors that could enhance the management of the persistent student unrest. In order to respond to this, the study provided answer to the following question; how can the threat associated with management of student unrest in university system be unmasked to pave way for smooth university operation devoid of social unrest? The study was underpinned by Ubuntu and lensed by Transformative Paradigm (TP). Participatory Action research design was adopted with the use of Focused Group Discussion (FGD) as a method of data collection from 8 selected university stakeholders. Socio-thematic Analysis (StA) was used to analyse the data. The study found out that campus environmentalism and drug abuse were the major threats while the uninterrupted university productivity and students' academic performance were found to be resultant effect of managing the threats. To this end, the study concluded that Ubuntu-like management style will enhance the management of threats hindering the university peace and tranquillity.

Introduction

Universities all over the world have experiences one or two crisis situations which are not limited to social and organisational unrests between the university staff unions and university authorities, students unions and university authorities, student to students' groups, among others (Yamnjoh, Konings, 2012; Pitan&Akindele, 2016; Manderson, 2016; Omodan&Dube, 2019). Many of these unrest have been linked to university management styles with various accusations that university authorities are mostly autocratic in dealing with their subordinates (Omodan, 2016). Prominent among these unrest are staged by students and their leaders, who at many time perceive their university management as an authority who must be confronted in order to make their voices and agitations hard. Student unrest in Nigerian universities, with many examples abound, are the crisis between the students and university authorities in the University of Ado Ekiti, in 2009, 2011 and 2014, ObafemiAwolowo University in 2009 and 2014, LadokeAkintola University, University of Ibadan, Lagos State University and University of Lagos, among others (Etadon, 2013; Odu, 2013; Premium Times, 2017, Omodan, 2019). These perpetual unrest situation caused by students as a result of one or more disagreement and dichotomies with institutional authorities had resulted into loss of life destruction properties and undue elongation of academic sessions (Fomunyan, 2017; Akparep, 2019).

In my observations, supported by literature, evidence exist that students oriented crisis, unrest and protest continue unabated in the university system. This is corroborated by Akeusola, Viatonu and Askhia (2012) Etadon (2013); Davies, Ekwere and Uyanga (2015) that, despite so much solutions that have been provided by the universities, scholars and government, student unrest is still at its peak in Nigeria tertiary institutions. From this, one could see that there are concerted efforts by the university authorities, government and the concerned stakeholders to put an end into the problem but it seems they are not cognisance of some social and human factors that is needed to ameliorate the problem. This is to further support the assertion of Sousa

and Moço(2017) that organisational management is not only meant to take care of people but also their environment and way of life. This is to argue that, there may be so many social and university climatic factors affecting the effective management, control and prevention of student unrest in the system. Identifying this, will give effective and efficient management space for the problem to be nipped in the bud. This kind of factor(s) may not be unconnected with university environment and the behaviours of it people such as students. Suffixed in the conclusion of Omodan (2019) and Omodan, Kolawole and Fakunle (2016) is that university climate which is synonymous with environmental factors has a great influence on the behaviours of stakeholders in school system.

From the above, one could argue that university management team when responding to student unrest might have neglected the power of environmental and social threat that is capable of influencing the behaviour of the stakeholders against themselves. That is, when the social and climatic influencers are unpleasant or anti-social, will evidently lead to anti-social behaviours of students, which is synonymous to crisis and/or unrest. This argument made a direct reference to the theory of Campus Ecology to corroborate the above conclusion that the relationships between organisms and their environment predict to a large extent the understanding of behaviour of the organism (Banning & McKinley, 1998). The theory was propounded by Banning in 1980 to predominantly describe the consequence of interaction between the college students and the campus environment (Banning, 1990).

Hence, one of the major contributions of campus ecological perspective to students' unrest is a systematic and comprehensive consideration of the campus environment as a factor that could threaten the peace of the university if not controlled (Davies, Ekwere&Uyanga, 2015). On the other hand, various social vices on campuses, such as campus cult activities, drug abuse and addiction, and examination malpractices among others is a resultant effect of various environmental influences mostly found within students' population on campuses (Aluede, Jimoh, Agwinede&Omoregie, 2015). All these, if not taken with all managerial seriousness could constitute a huge deficit to the management of crises in universities because when there is lack of adequate security, presences of environmental hazards, unpleasant classroom ecology, and conduciveness of students' and staff personnel services, coupled with external interference will likely propel a negative behaviour. This is tantamount to breaking down of law and order since environment and individuals are determinants of human behaviours (Lewin, 1936). In other to inject good and productive behaviours into students and other stakeholders in the university system, the place of Ubuntu as relational theory will help to unpack the trajectories of managing student unrest in the universities.

Ubuntu as theoretical framework for the study

This study is underpinned by Ubuntu. Ubuntu as a philosophy of oneness and humanity (Omodan&Tsotetsi, 2019) is traceable to some African Languages such as IsiXhosa, IsiZulu, IsiNdebele and IsiSwati which, in a broader sense means unity and humanness (Tutu, 2004; Bolden, 2014). In the claim of Omodan (2019), Ubuntu emanated from Africa here people lived together in harmony without recourse to their diversities. From the Zulu language, Lefa (2015) claim that Ubuntu is associated with the words; "umuntungumuntungabantu" which means "a person is a person through other people". In the same vein, the Zulu word "simunye" which could be interpreted as "we are one in unity" (Marunda, 2015; Bangura, 2017; Variri and Variri 2019) or "we are united". Ubuntu was also called African philosophy that is likened to oneness, unity, brotherhood, love and compassion (Bondai&Kaputa, 2016; Omodan, 2020). Ubuntu was identified by Tutu (1999) as having mutual way of doing things, generous, empathy, honesty and communal commitment. From the forgoing, to say that Ubuntu is principled towards humanness, oneness, solidarity, strength in unity, resilience, compassion, and empathy in not out of place.

These principle of Ubuntu was categorised into three by Mogadime, Mentz, Armstrong and Holtam (2010), they are spirituality, interdependence and unity. He argued that spirituality is the idea that people must live in harmony with one another and that this is a call from the Supreme Being. The second principle according to them is interdependence, which they claimed to mean that, people are dependent on one another, that no one exist in isolation. That is, the seniors, and the subordinates, the equals could only survive in their unity and a combined strength. And the third is unity, they believed that unity in diversity will enhance the progress and

development of people who share the same mission and vision. This could be likened to the university community where different set of stakeholders work together for one purpose which is to produce high quality graduate for economic sustainability (Daniela, Salvioni&Raffaella, 2017). Reflecting this on spirituality, the university authorities who are assumed to be privilege, must utilise all the available resources to selflessly serve and protect those that are assume powerless, in this case could mean students. This is because Spatiality according to Ngunjiri (2016) is when one provides selfless services to protect and benefit the under-privileged. This theory is, therefore, relevant to this study because it principles are those that could inject good organisational and people's behaviours most especially in university system. To corroborate this, Brydon-Mille and Coghlan (2014) reiterates that Ubuntu propel the ethics and commitment into people which is meant to change their behaviour for good. That is, when the spirit of Ubuntu is adopted in University community, the people and the environmental behaviours will likely reflect that of love, unity, oneness, commitment, collaboration and connectedness which in my argument, is tantamount to actualisation of the university goal and objectives devoid of social unrest between the students and university authorities.

Research Question

In order to achieve the above, as postulated by Ubuntu, the following research question guided the study;

1. How can the threat associated with management of student unrest in university system be unmasked to pave way for smooth university operation devoid of social unrest?

Research Objectives

By responding to the above research question, the following research objectives was raised to pilot the study;

1. The study examined the threats associated with the management of student unrest in the university system in Nigeria.
2. The study also investigated the possible implication for the effective management of the threats.

Methodology

Research Paradigm

The study falls under Transformative Paradigm (TP) because it aims and objective is to transform university community from the state of social instability as a result of student unrest into a state of stability devoid of social unrest. The TP based on its axiology, promotes moral, cultural respect, social justice and human rights (Mertens, 2010). It equally addresses inequities and reciprocity (Mertens, 2017). From it ontological views, the reality that shaped the social issues such as crisis management in university community is politically inclined, sociality, historically and culturally embedded. This is to confirm that reality exists outside the mind (Elshafe, 2013). The epistemological stance of this paradigm in line with this study is based on the social relationships, reality, sociality and the power differential among the researched. This is why the establishment of interactive relationship is needed to be able to understand and deal with power differentials within community members (Mertens, 2012). This paradigm is appropriate because is further gives hope to the theory of Ubuntu in its mission to transform university community. In the same vein, the methodical design of the TP also falls within the purview of participatory action researchers (Mertens, 2005) which also focus on the dynamics of emancipation (Dube, 2016). This is why the study adopted Participatory Action Research (PAR) as a research design.

Participatory Action Research as Research Design

Since the study is hoping to provide solution to social issues, student unrest in university system, it is then expedient to involve all the stakeholders in the system to jointly share experience in solving the problem. The Participatory Action Research then become relevant. PAR is traceable to radical tradition towards participation, action and development of knowledge to respond to social injustices, inclusivity and above all, it empowers and emancipates the marginalised (Khan &Chovanec 2010:34). In my argument, PAR requires equal participation between the researchers and the researched who are enlightened to identify, analyse and address issues at hand. This definition shows that PAR is a bundle of activities that encompass investigation (research), educationally work and act towards changing the status quo. Subjecting this research process into PAR, gives opportunity for the people face by the problem to jointly provide solution using their experience,

actions and inactions. This is confirmed by Tshelane (2013) that PAR values indigenous and local knowledge of the marginalized groups as a basis for revolutionary actions, which can improve the lives of people. Therefore, using PAR to design this study enables me to get into the stakeholders of the university, bring them together within the principle of fairness, equal participation and dismantled power plays to ensure solution to the problem of students' unrest in the system.

Method of Data Collection

In order to implement PAR, Focus Group Discussion (FGD) was used to collect data from the participants, this is appropriate because it speaks to bringing people together, talk together, share experience and views together for the purpose of solving problem. Besides, Romm (2015) opined that the use of FGD, interviews, survey and threaded discussions are practical ways of ensuring free participation of people while providing solution to their problem. In complimenting the above, this data generation method according to Escalada and Heong (2014) enables the research group to obtain insights into participants' perceptions, needs, problems, beliefs and reasons for certain practices. The researcher then engaged the participants in three different meetings, the first meeting was to inform them about the research and the method used. In the second meeting, we discussed the research question and the objectives and the last meeting was made to cross-check the interpretation of data. This enables the participants to know the meanings given to their utterances as to whether the interpretation and analysis actually represent their original views.

Participants and the Selection of Participants

The population of this study comprised eight stakeholders in university community in Nigeria. The stakeholders include, two students' leaders, two university lecturers, two university authorities, two both external and internal securities saddled with protection of lives and properties in university community. These stakeholders were selected using convenient sampling techniques. The technique was used because it is less time consuming as the subject is quick and easy to be approached. It is expedient to use this kind of sampling because this set of participants are sometimes highly placed which in most cases, restrictions are placed around their offices, except if you are coming on an invitation. Hence, the main assumption associated with convenience sampling is that all the members of the target population are capable of providing the needed information because they are homogenous (Etikan, Musa & Alkassim, 2016:3). Therefore, considering the nature of their experiences, actions and inactions in terms student unrest and its management, this technique is considered appropriate because it enables researchers to make use of participants who are easy or convenient to be approached (Alvi, 2016:23) among the targeted population.

Method of Data Analysis

The study adopted Socio-thematic Analysis (StA) to make sense of the data, this method of analysis was propounded by Omodan (2019), as a best method to dealing with social issues in research. This according to him enables the researcher to study and understand the sociality of the participants. That is, it gives more light into how the participants relationships are framed that might be responsible for the social unrest between the university authority and the students. This method according to him is a combination of Braun & Clarke (2006)'s thematic analysis and Conversational Analysis that was described by Omodan (2019) and Nordquist, (2019) as doing things with words to perform social actions such as describing, agreeing, questioning offering, and talking, assumed to be understood when people act out their sociality through conversation. Therefore, StA take the cognisance of the six step of doing thematic analysis by familiarising with data, generating code or coding, identifying the themes, reviewing the themes, defining and or naming the themes, and producing the reports/analysis using *conversationality* (Omodan, 2019). That is, all the categorized statements under the respective themes are interpreted with the sociality test to uncover the social dependency and independency among the participants. The method, therefore, helps me to break down the data into relevant themes according the objectives of the study with analytical understanding of the power differentials and the kind of relationships that exist among them.

Ethical Consideration

This research is a part of a bigger project and received ethical approval with ethical clearance number UFS-HSD2018/1105 from the University of the Free State, South Africa. All the prescribed directives in term of ethics were observed. The consent of the participants were obtained and they were allowed to either accept or reject the participation. Even they were given freedom to withdraw at the later stage should they feel uncomfortable with the research process. They were ensured that their identities will never be revealed to any third parties without their notice or prior approval from them. Based on this, their identities were represented with pseudo names during the data presentation and analysis. They were represented as follow; University Authority (UA1&2), Student Leader (SL1&2), University Lecturer (UL1&2), Security Personnel (SP1&2).

Data Presentation and Analysis

In data, as gathered with the use of par is presented and analyzed below using socio-thematic analysis. the data were categorized based on the two objective raised above; the threats associated with management of student crises in university system and the possible success associated with effective management of crisis between students and university authorities.

Threats Associated with Management of Student Crises in University System

This section dealt with the analysis of data as thematised according to those conversations falling under the likely threats that could hinder the management of student oriented crisis in university system. Data was rationalized under the following sub-headings: Campus Environmentalism and Drug Abuse.

Campus Environmentalism

University environmentalism in this study refers to such factors that fall under school climate and environmental ecology with which external and internal relationships of the university are not an exemption. That is, a pleasant environment is likely to produce peaceful environment and if otherwise, has become a threat to the existence of such organization. These are factors that influence behaviours of students and other stakeholders in university system (Hodgetts& Altman, 2078). Since this is confirmed to have a significant influence on the behaviours of students, then it becomes a threat where the university environment is disposing negatively to the university community. Besides, the discussion with participants revealed that when these environmental factors are not well controlled, they are capable of threatening the peaceful relationships and co-existence of university stakeholders, more especially students and university authorities. The evidence is shown in the below conversations:

UA1: *“Environment is an influential factor that cannot be under-carpeted. If the environment is not favourable, results to be expected will be negatively inclined and vice versa”*

SP1: *“The ability of government to decode or interpret signs coming from the environment go a long way in ensuring stability in that system.*

SP2: *Crisis don’t just assume, it starts with grumbling and probably with just a minor protest as it has been in Nigeria”*

From the above conversations, it is confirmed that factors of university environment are as important as the university itself. If those factors such as adequate security, hazards and pollution, classroom ecology, university and community relationships, external and internal interference are not positively discharged or dispensed, they will lead to negative outcomes. Such outcomes include, but not limited to protest, crises, and misunderstanding among the university stakeholders. Inability of university to manage all these factors according to Lewin (1936) is detrimental of human behaviours, which is tantamount to breaking down of law and order. In university environment, this is not an exemption. The second statement also confirmed how detrimental the campus environmentalism could be to the university’s peaceful existence by recommending to the governing council which is the top management body of the university to devise means to which these threats could be controlled. By so doing, this will enable them to detect any likely occurrence of resistance coming from the students. It is confirmed by these statement that crises do not just happen. They start from grumbling and protest as a result of environmental dissatisfaction. Hence, environmentalism is not only

restricted to just the physical environment, but also concerns with the culture of the university, the individual differences based on experiences and knowledge applications to issues. This is exposed as followed:

SL2: *“the culture that the students and management has will somehow be different but needs to be blended as much as possible or else, this becomes a big threat to the establishment”*

UL1: *“The view of each party differs and if not ameliorate to consider the environmental factors then, crisis is inevitable”*

The above statements show that both the university authorities and students view issues from different perspectives which could be regarded as students’ culture and management culture. This culture tends to be in opposition to one each other. This could be the way students respond to issues from management and the way management responds to issues from students. This diversity in stakeholders’ culture in the system needs to be ameliorated or else, it will spell doom for the existence of the university. On the second statement, it shows that judgment should be assigned based on the background of the participants because each social background affects the way they behave. That is, students appear to be too demanding based on their level of understanding and youthfulness, while the school management are usually elderly persons who as a result of cultural values, demand to be respected and be listened to. If these are not done in accordance with the principle of cultural background and individual difference, it becomes a huge environmental threat to the system. Therefore, it is logical and socially acceptable to conclude that campus environmentalism is a threat to the students-management relationships in university system.

Drug Abuse

Drug abuse is a general phenomenon which may not only be attributed to university community alone, but the trajectory is that it is common among the youth and youth constitutes at least 70% of the members of universities. Various crises happening in the universities have been one way or the other linked to substance addiction and drug abuse in the system (Aluede, et al., 2015). Among other substances that are usually misused on campus are narcotics, cannabis, hallucinogens, alcoholic beverages, tobacco, inhalants, caffeine beverages, and all forms of stimulants (Amayo&Wangai, 1994). This is adjudged to be responsible for violence and crisis in the university community. The misuse of these substances is significant to violent and criminal behaviour of students (Sugut&Mugasia, 2014:127). Hence, this is also confirmed during our discussion. See below:

UL2: *“Alcoholism is a general phenomenon that the society is battling with which now a major threat to any organization including schools”*

UA2: *“Students become difficult to manage most especially when they are under influence of drug and other substances”*

SL1: *“when we drink too much, back then it gives us strength to fight on. This no doubt leads to negative social influence”*

The first statement is buttressing the fact that drug abuse is not only peculiar to university alone, but the entire society. From the social perspective, one could see that the menace is somewhat beyond the control of a singular organisation. Hence, this makes it a huge threat to the university system because students under the influence of any substances will be difficult to manage. Such person or student will not own him or herself to their thinking faculty and may behave abnormally, which is open to violence and other anti-social vices. This is confirmed by the second statement and buttressed by the literature that drug abuse has a significant correlation on university riot and students’ violence (Florence, 2010:127). This is confirmed by the last statement. This participant confirmed that even students’ leaders at some point drink excess alcohol to enable them fight and fight to a standstill. Therefore, the use or the abuse of drug is not only peculiar to unserious students, but the leaders of the students also engage in such possibly to give them unrelenting strength of resistance. Therefore, this is appropriate to logically and socially conclude that drug abuse is a threat to managing university system.

Possible implication associated with effective management of student unrest

This section focused on the analysis of participants’ statements that fall under the possible implication that will be recorded by the entire university if issues of student unrest is nipped in the bud by the university

management. This was done under the sub-themes as follows: university productivity; students' academic performance.

University productivity

Productivity and effectiveness form the goal and objectives of the university system. This is, therefore, one of the drives of all the stakeholders to strive to ensure not just to graduate students, but to ensure that they produce quality and worthwhile graduates who would be impactful and contribute to the development of the society and economic development of the nation at large. In achieving this, there comes the importance of peace and relative tranquillity. The presence of peace is a point of motivation to the people in university community to unanimously work together to achieve the target objectives. This, according to Yaya, Uzohue, and Akintayo (2016) is expedient because motivation has a significant contribution to productivities of the subordinates. Hence, the discussion conducted with the research participants also showed that when there is relative peace and tranquillity, more especially when there is amiable relationship between the students and university authorities, it will enhance optimum productivity in the system. See below:

SL2: *“When there is peace on campuses, properties will not be destroyed, new students will want to come and study there, smooth running of academic calendar which will encourage parents to bring their wards to the school leading to more financial increase”*

This statement shows that the absence of conflict in the university community is socially synonymous to lack of vandalism, which will protect the campus from any kind of anti-social behaviours. This impression will also attract more parents and prospective university students to have a good mindset towards university education. This is because every student will know that they will graduate as and when due, unlike my own experience as an undergraduate where I spent six years for a four years programme. This was not because I failed, but because there was no stable academic calendar and there were disruptions day-in day-out. This shows that, the university at that time was unable to achieve its aims and objectives as and when due. Moreover, students were also affected as it put their personal and academic achievement in jeopardy. Therefore, it is socially logical to conclude that peace among stakeholders is synonymous with productivities.

UA1: *“a crisis free university community gives a certain level of assurance nationally and internationally of good moral and academic standard”*

SP1: *“When there is relative peaceful co-existence in the university system, the university itself will be productive and have a brighter societal future for its graduates”*

The first statement relates to peace with a good name, meaning that the absence of crisis in the university will create a good name for the university, both nationally and internationally. This could also be interpreted that such university is operating under the presupposed moral and international academic standard (UNESCO, 2002). This is not enough as the second statement revealed that the presence of peace ensures productivity. This means that, when the university stakeholders enjoy harmonious team work and relationships, it will not only affect the university positively, but the students will also be guaranteed a brighter future in the society. This is in line with the conclusion of Eneh (2015) that this high level of productivity could only be assured in a violence free environment.

Students' Academic Performance

Students' academic performance in no small measure is one of the objectives of the university management because this defines whether the university is effective or not. It is generally believed that staff efficiency if not translated to students' academic performance is of no use. Therefore, students are expected to showcase the academic quality dispensed to them by having good academic achievement (Karimi, 2008). However, there are many factors responsible for this. These factors according to Ohiwerei and Onimawo (2016) are not limited to intelligence and socio-political background of students, but also determined by the level of anti-social behaviours of students, such as protest among others. This does not only appear in literature, as the discussion conducted with my research participants also revealed that relative peace and tranquillity are significant to students' academic performance and achievement. This is shown below:

SL2: *“when all indices are put in place for the sake of peace, students understands they have lesser challenges other than how to study hard and make the society works”*

UL2: *“My brothers, when there is peace, students will be happy to take learning to a higher level then there will be productivity and student academic performance will increase”*

The sociality in the above statement is not far from the fact that the availability of all peace apparatus becomes a motivation for students to study hard for their development and also the development of the society, which is the outward target of all education systems according to National Policy on Education (Federal Government of Nigeria, 2013). The second statement also predicts the mutuality in the conversation without any power play among the conversant. Irrespective of their classes and position, the call for peace is unanimously agreed to be the propeller of students’ academic performance. Moreover, it was also confirmed that both social and psychological stability of all stakeholders in the university is related positively to academic performance as shown in the below conversation;

UL1: *“Peace of mind to study, psychology stability, stable lecture time and examination time which in turn reflect on the students’ academic performance and university outputs”*

This implies that, both psycho-social states revolve around students including the physical factors such as stable lecture time and examination time, which are all predictors of academic performance. Therefore, from these inferences, one could logically and socially conclude that both internal and outwardly states of existence have a significant correlation with students’ academic behaviours. Hence, to ensure students’ effectiveness in university system, there must be a relational peace between the students and the university authority.

Presentation of Findings based on the objectives

This section presents findings as it relates to the constructs on the likely threats that may hinder the effective management of crisis between the students and the university authorities. The threats highlighted in the findings are Campus Environmentalism and Drug Abuse. Also, findings related to success envisaged when crises in university system are well and adequately controlled and managed. These possible successes are discussed under the following themes: university productivity and students’ academic performance.

Campus Environmentalism

It was found that adequate security, hazards and pollution, classroom ecology, university and community relationships, external and internal interference that contribute to what makes campus environmentalism are some of the factors that threaten the management of crisis between the students and the university authorities. This is to say, if these factors are not positively discharged, they are capable of leading to negative outcomes such as protests, crises, and misunderstanding among the university stakeholders. It was also revealed that diversity in stakeholders’ culture in the system needs to be ameliorated because this affects the behaviours of stakeholders. That is, students appear to be too demanding based on their level of understanding and youthfulness, while the school management are usually elderly persons who as a result of cultural values, demand to be respected and be listened to. The findings of Omodan et al., (2016) compliment this that school environmental climate is positively related to the overall effectiveness of schools among which is universities. This is not far from the theory of Ubuntu that when there is love, oneness, unity, compassion and collaboration among the stakeholder predict to a large extent the display of productive behaviour of the organism (Mogadime, et al., 2010). On the other hand, when the environment is negative, the result will be negative. This, if not controlled, becomes a great threat to the existence of university management (Davis, Ekwere&Uyanga, 2015). Hence, it is rational to conclude that campus environmentalism is a threat militating against the students-management relationships.

Drug Abuse

Drug abuse is found to be another threat to the management of students’ related issues in university community. This is not found solely by university system, but it is found to be a general problem affecting the entire society. It was found that this abuse of drugs such as narcotics, cannabis, hallucinogens, alcoholic beverages, tobacco, inhalants, and caffeine beverages are not only consumed by the unserious students, but at some instances taken by students’ leaders to enable them do and undo. If this continues, then it becomes

dangerous for peace to rain in university community. This is in consonance with the findings of Florence (2010) that drug abuse has a great influence on riot and students' violence. This also justified the findings of Sugut and Mugasia (2014) that drug abuse is highly significant with high reliability co-efficient to the university violence. On the part of Ubuntu, when these students are taking care of, then the university authorities show them love and make them to feel that they are part of the system, when the students are provided with all they need to be successful, they may resist any act of drugging and other social vices. Therefore, the misuse or abuse of substance remain a threat to the management of university system.

University Productivity

From the above discussion, it was revealed that when there is absolute peace and tranquillity in the university system, it is tantamount to speedy actualization of the set predetermined goals and objectives. This in turn will positively reflect in the general productivity of the system. It was also deduced that the presence of peaceful co-existence will enable the students to graduate as and when due. All these are elements of productivity with evidence for societal development. This will not only motivate university authorities for performance, but also stand as a point of conformability to students. This according to Yaya et al., (2016) becomes unavoidable because motivation significantly contribute to subordinates' performance for productivity. This is not in contrast to conclusion of Eneh (2015) that high level of productivity could only be guaranteed in a violence free environment. This is, however, confirmed that university system will record uninterrupted successes when there is peace and relative tranquillity.

Students' Academic Performance

The findings showed that when there is no rancor or crisis at universities, it will affect positively the academic performance of the students. This is deduced from the fact that positive reflection of both psycho-social state of the students, as well as physical factors such as stable lecture times and examination time will motivate students to more academic achievement. This is in consonance with the assumption of Ubuntu that described the essence of motivation on stakeholders' unity (Variri and Variri 2019). That is, peaceful environment is a pointer to students' motivation to study hard for better academic performance. The findings of Ohiwerei and Onimawo (2016) indicate that factors such as strike actions, student protest and other antisocial activities are also accountable for the performance of students. This is to say that when there is no peace, there may not be record of dependable academic performance. This is also supported by the conclusion of Ajayi (2014) that incessant strikes action in universities has inadvertently affected the academics of university students, which usually poses a lot of challenges to their study duration, performance in examinations and their final grading. From this, one could therefore conclude that the presence of peace and relative tranquillity will lead to students' academic performance.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The above exploration has successfully opened up a way to which social space of the university system could be transformed. Among these transformation process is the practice of Ubuntu as an input, process, and output remedy for management of student unrest. Campus environmentalism such as classroom ecology, provision of conducive teaching and learning space for students, university and community relationships, internal external interference, and drug abuse are the major factors that threaten the relationships between the students and the university authority thereby making the system unpleasant to be controlled. On the other hand, when this threats are effectively managed, the aftermath effect will ensure uninterrupted university productivity and students' academic performance. This in my conclusion is that, campus environmentalism and drug abuse are the dimension of student unrest in university and that when they are controlled, prevent and managed, will promote university goal and objectives. Based on this, the following recondition was made that the university authorities must take cognizance of, not only the people and the facilities available in the system, but also ensure that university environmental factors are taken into consideration. This is because it was found that campus environmentalism as well as drug abuse are the major social threat that is militating against the management prowess of the university. Therefore, university management must be aware and deal with it according to the surrounding situations. The issue of drugging must be addressed

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